

CONCEPT FOR IMPROVING THE TEACHING OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE AS THE STATE LANGUAGE IN OUR REPUBLIC

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***Abstract.** The article presents information on the initial period and subsequent development of teaching the state language to representatives of various nationalities residing in Uzbekistan, as well as on the first curricula, textbooks, dictionaries, and phrasebooks created for the Uzbek language. With independence, the scope of research on teaching Uzbek to representatives of other nationalities has significantly expanded; textbooks, teaching aids, and dictionaries for Uzbek language instruction in Russian-medium groups have been produced, and state educational standards have been developed. However, the fact that representatives of different nationalities living in our multi-ethnic republic still do not meet the requirements for administrative documentation and oral communication in the state language indicates that many problems remain in this area. The present concept proposes ways to overcome these challenges, to improve the requirements of state educational standards, to raise the levels of acquired competencies from A1 to C2, to address issues of organizing Uzbek language teaching based on national characteristics, to modernize the linguodidactic foundations, and to outline the expected results.*

***Keywords:** language education, Uzbek language, methodology reform, teaching Uzbek as a state language, aims and objectives, state educational standards (SES), agglutinative structure of Uzbek, existing challenges, priority directions, developing competencies, lifelong education, continuity.*

INTRODUCTION

The practical importance of language in society is extremely significant, so every country devotes significant attention to the teaching and learning of languages. The ability of all citizens living in Uzbekistan to communicate freely in the state language of our republic and express their thoughts orally and in writing is a crucial factor in ensuring that the people of our republic live in harmony and friendship, work together, and contribute to the further development of our country's economy.

In our republic, instruction in public schools is conducted in seven languages: Uzbek, Karakalpak, Russian, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Tajik, and Turkmen, and is taught as both their native and official languages. The primary goal of teaching Uzbek as the state language in the republic's comprehensive schools where instruction is conducted in other languages, as well as in groups taught in Russian and Karakalpak at subsequent stages of the continuing education system, is to ensure sufficient practical mastery of Uzbek as the state language for their social activities, as well as to develop fluent oral and written communication skills in various interpersonal situations.

It is widely acknowledged that citizens of various nationalities living in our republic recognize that knowing Uzbek merely as a means of spoken and oral communication is not enough. It has become essential for them to be able to speak and write competently in the state language,

as well as possess written office skills in the state language. It should be noted that a significant portion of citizens living in our country receive their education in schools and Russian groups where instruction is conducted in other languages. Effective organization of Uzbek language instruction in these schools and groups is a matter of national importance, necessitating the identification of new conceptual approaches to improving the teaching of the state language, identifying specific aspects of enhancing the effectiveness of Uzbek language education, and identifying the most advanced methods and their effective implementation.

The granting of Uzbek the status of a state language in connection with the Law "On the State Language" and the attainment of independence opened up broad horizons for the further development of our native language. Our native language has become the primary means of communication in our republic and has begun to be widely used as a scientific, artistic, and official language. The adoption of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Program for the Implementation of the Law "On the State Language" in 1990, the Law "On the Introduction of the Uzbek Alphabet Based on the Latin Script" in 1993, the new version of the Law "On the State Language" in 1995, and the Resolution on Amending the State Program for the Implementation of this Law in 1996 were important steps towards the further development of the Uzbek language. The study, teaching, and research of the Uzbek language, as well as the publication of scientific and artistic works, and educational literature in the new Uzbek script, have expanded widely. The establishment of the Alisher Navoi Tashkent State University of the Uzbek Language and Literature on May 13, 2016, marked an important stage in the historical development of the Uzbek language.

It has been extensively documented that Decree No. UF 5850 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 21, 2019, "On measures to radically enhance the prestige and status of the Uzbek language as the state language," opened new chapters in the development of the Uzbek language, aimed at preserving and further developing the native language, ensuring the full implementation of the state language in our country, further improving the system of teaching the state language in educational institutions, and assessing its proficiency. The Concept attached to the Decree places special emphasis on creating favorable conditions for the study of the Uzbek language by representatives of all nationalities and ethnic groups living in our country. Its implementation requires further improvement of programs developed in the Uzbek language and a radical improvement in the content and methodology of textbooks. This Concept envisages the teaching of Uzbek as a second language to representatives of different nationalities living in the republic, based on continuity and in accordance with national characteristics. It is aimed at organizing education taking into account the goals, objectives and principles of teaching Uzbek as the state language in schools with instruction in Russian, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Tajik, Turkmen and Karakalpak languages, based on the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", "On the State Language" and "National Personnel Training Program".

The reforms being implemented in the education sector in the renewed Uzbekistan are aimed at rapidly awakening the peoples of the East, reviving in our children the talent of our great ancestors for the natural sciences and multilingualism, reorganizing preschool education as the first, initial stage of the continuous education system, and defining measures to begin providing basic knowledge in core subjects from this stage. The ability of all citizens living in Uzbekistan to communicate fluently in the state language of the republic is a key factor in ensuring that the people of our country live in harmony and friendship, work together, and continue to improve our country's economy. Accordingly, the main goal of teaching Uzbek (the state language) in the

continuous compulsory education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to develop students' competence in applying acquired knowledge and skills in the Uzbek language in their work activities, based on the communicative-verbal principle. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to develop a sufficient level of knowledge, skills, and abilities in the field of communicative, speech, and linguistic competence in the Uzbek language in accordance with the requirements of the state educational standard. Based on this goal, this concept:

organize Uzbek language instruction based on continuity and continuity at all levels of education (preschool education, general education, lyceums and colleges, undergraduate and graduate programs);

create an effective methodology for teaching Uzbek as a second language, develop a system of exercises and assignments that facilitate the acquisition of the agglutinative properties of the Uzbek language and their application in the educational process;

ensure mutual (horizontal) and interstage (vertical) continuity of verbal communication skills—grammatical theory—and literary reading in the process of teaching the Uzbek language;

modernization of Uzbek language curricula and textbooks aimed at developing verbal communication skills and the creation of a national, interdisciplinary, integrated system utilizing advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies in Uzbek language teaching.

the development of computer-based learning programs, multimedia tools, and electronic textbooks aimed at teaching Uzbek as a second language and their active implementation in the education system were identified as key objectives. These objectives are aimed at developing students' practical speaking skills in Uzbek, gradually transforming them into competencies, and developing their ability to freely apply acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities in various communication situations—that is, developing verbal competence.

THE STATUS OF LANGUAGE STUDY IN UZBEKISTAN

The teaching of the Uzbek language to representatives of other nationalities began in 1906, and the first research on the teaching of the Uzbek language began in the 1930s. The teaching of the Uzbek language to representatives of other nationalities is associated with the establishment of Russian-language schools in Turkestan [1; 2]. Before 1917, Mullah Solikhodja Kichkinakhodjaev, S. M. Gramensky, Usman Dadamukhamedov, Muhammadrasul Rasulov, Ali Askar Kalinin, Saidrasul Saidazizov, Muhammad Amin Muhammad Karimov, and Kamoliddin Kakhkhorov taught Uzbek to Russians in Russian-language schools. In particular, according to S. Nazarova, the activities of these schools were responsible for the appearance of the first textbooks dedicated to teaching the Uzbek language to representatives of other nationalities living in Turkestan [1, 19].

The inclusion of the Uzbek language as a core subject in the curriculum began in 1933, and by this time, the Uzbek language had begun to be taught not only in schools but also in higher education institutions. In particular, the creation of a special Uzbek language department for Russian groups at the Turkestan Oriental Institute and the organization of Uzbek language study in state institutions based on a special program led to significant changes in the teaching of Uzbek in Russian groups [3]. The first Uzbek language curricula and dictionaries were compiled by Russian methodologists. In the works of S. Nazarova and K. Kholikberdiev, V. F. Druzinin, K. S. There is information about the first vocabulary minimums compiled for students in Russian schools by Koblov, A. Klimenko, I. A. Enileeva [1; 2]. In particular, K. Kholikberdiev highly valued the scientific and pedagogical work of the famous Turkologist I. A. Bat'manov as a scientist who managed to "correctly demonstrate the methods of teaching the Uzbek language, the order of

studying Uzbek sounds and grammatical material" [2, 21]. Indeed, a number of programs and manuals published by I. A. Bat'manov for teachers of the Uzbek language were an important factor in the creation of the didactic foundations of Uzbek language education in those years [3; 4].

In the subsequent development of Uzbek language education, one can see that some scholars also addressed issues of comparative grammar of the Uzbek and Russian languages, while others devoted their work related to Uzbek language education primarily to the creation of dictionaries and glossaries [5; 6; 7; 8; 9]. After independence, special attention was paid to the creation of textbooks and teaching aids for Russian-language schools [10; 11; 12; 13; 14]. It is important to emphasize that from our independence, the range of scientific research on teaching Uzbek to representatives of other nationalities also expanded. A number of scientific papers have been published on issues of teaching Uzbek in Russian-language schools, higher and secondary specialized educational institutions, as well as teaching Uzbek in Russian-language groups in preschool educational institutions. In this regard, we can cite the works of M. Ergasheva on enriching students' speech with verbs at the level of general secondary education [15], G. Akhrova on teaching auxiliary verbs [16], F. Umarova on teaching auxiliary verbs [17], G. Akhmedova on teaching artificial words [18], M. Rikhsieva, D. Toshkhodjaeva on text composition [19; 20] and G. Mukhamadjonova on the development of speech of Russian-speaking students in extracurricular activities [21]. Unfortunately, subsequent research on the methods of teaching the Uzbek language was carried out only within the framework of individual topics at a specific educational level, and practically did not cover the issues of studying the Uzbek language in continuity and continuity between educational levels. On the issues of teaching the Uzbek language at the level of higher education, one can cite the research of

M. Karakhodjaeva on the methodology of developing professional speech of students in non-philological groups on the basis of verbs [22], S. Adilova on the topic of "Organization of classes in the Uzbek language using computer technologies" [23], M. Djuraev on the topic of "Development of methods for teaching Uzbek as a state language" [24], Z. Salisheva on the topic of "Improving the methodology of developing monologue speech of students in classes in the Uzbek language (in Russian groups)" [25]. The development of professional speech of future specialists in non-philological universities is one of the most important and pressing issues awaiting solution. The candidate dissertations of M. Karakhodjaeva, G. Kurbonova, N. Dadadjonova and the doctoral dissertation of G. Asilova are devoted to the study of these issues [22; 26; 25; 28]. In particular, the study of M. Karakhodjaeva, devoted to the enrichment of professional speech of students of Russian groups with verb constructions in the Uzbek language, is significant in that it highlights the issues of word compatibility in the Uzbek language [22], and the doctoral work of G. Asilova is devoted to the development of professional communicative competence in the state language of students of Russian groups in customs and tax fields [27].

It can be clearly observed that among these studies, it is worth noting the research work of G. Akhmedova on the topic of "Methodological foundations for enriching students' speech with artificial words in Uzbek language lessons (using the example of schools with Russian as the language of instruction)", dedicated to a very relevant topic [18]. This paper examines the importance of artificial words in expanding the vocabulary of Russian-speaking students and the need to consider their active and passive use in speech when teaching derivational suffixes in the Uzbek language. Since the issues of the active and passive lexical and grammatical minimum of the Uzbek language and their proper distribution between the stages of Uzbek language learning

are considered among the most pressing and pending problems today, this research can be considered one of the studies of a new direction in the field of Uzbek language teaching methods.

The findings indicate that specialized research devoted to the teaching of the Uzbek language in Russian groups of secondary specialized and vocational educational institutions has not been conducted. R. Niyozmetova's doctoral dissertation is devoted to the teaching of Uzbek literature in Russian groups of academic lyceums [29], and Sh. Yuldasheva's candidate's dissertation is devoted to the teaching of the state language in academic lyceums with the Karakalpak language of instruction [30]. In particular, R. Niyozmetova's research work emphasizes that Uzbek literature is taught in Uzbek language lessons at the general secondary education level through the reading of fiction, but due to the lack of inclusion of materials for reading fiction in the curricula of Russian groups of academic lyceums, there is a gap in the system of continuous education [29]. The doctoral dissertation of Kh.S. Mukhitdinova is directly devoted to the issues of ensuring continuity between educational levels in teaching the Uzbek language in Russian groups, and the work describes the existing problems of continuous teaching of the state language of our republic at the levels of general secondary education, secondary specialized and higher education, as well as ways to overcome them [31].

From the description of the research works conducted on teaching the Uzbek language in Russian groups in the period after independence, it is clear that the majority of these research works developed one or another feature of teaching the Uzbek language in Russian groups at a certain educational stage and were aimed to a greater extent at developing the oral and written speech of pupils and students in the Uzbek language. It is known that before the reform, Uzbek language lessons in Russian-language schools, as well as in Russian-language groups at higher education institutions, were taught using the native language method. That is, as in native language lessons in national groups, information on all sections of the Uzbek language was provided in a somewhat abbreviated form: phonetics, vocabulary, morphology, syntax. The main difference was that grammar rules were taught briefly and primarily in Russian, and in some cases, in both Uzbek and Russian. Exercises were also usually limited to purely grammar exercises and the translation of phraseological sentences into Russian or Uzbek. As a result of this teaching method, especially since the rules were also taught in Russian, Russian-speaking students were limited to memorizing grammar rules and, as noted above, understood Uzbek but could not speak it. These textbooks practically lacked a system of exercises and assignments that would encourage students to communicate orally, foster their desire to speak Uzbek, or guide them in constructing phrases from words, sentences from phrases, and texts from sentences.

In essence, the main goal of teaching Uzbek in schools and Russian-language groups with instruction in other languages is not to teach students Uzbek grammar, but to develop their speaking skills in Uzbek. Based on this, in recent years, Uzbek language curricula for schools with instruction in Russian and other languages have been developed based on the communicative-speech principle and the functional-semantic principles of second language teaching. The resulting textbooks are aimed at developing essential grammatical knowledge, rules for combining words and phrases, taking into account speech needs and the purpose of expressing thoughts, as well as teaching Uzbek using existing tools. State educational standards have been developed and a number of textbooks have been created based on these principles. However, the lack of continuity between grammatical knowledge and speech acts, as well as continuity between educational levels, prevented the development of the ability to apply acquired knowledge in practice. The language system is extremely complex and multifaceted, and learning a specific language is even more

challenging, as it involves a number of important aspects, such as speech development, speech skills, and the emergence of speech situations. Many scholars emphasize the importance of objective factors such as the differences between the target language and the native language, and the role and prestige of the target language in a given society.

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING THE UZBEK LANGUAGE IN THE MODERN STAGE

There is substantial evidence to suggest that the Law "On the State Language" and the attainment of independence, the Uzbek language was granted the status of a state language, and the native language began to be widely used as the primary means of communication in our republic. As a result of teaching the Uzbek language in all education systems, publishing educational, scientific, and fiction literature in Uzbek, and maintaining records in Uzbek, our republic has achieved a number of successes in the practice of the state language. The introduction of a competency-based approach to teaching foreign languages, including Uzbek, in developed countries has led to fundamental reforms in our education system: state educational standards based on basic and subject-specific competencies have been improved, curricula have been restructured to ensure meaningful coherence between speech topics, theoretical grammar knowledge, literary reading, and continuity between levels of education, and textbooks have been modernized.

However, despite the progress achieved, the unsatisfactory results and the fact that Russian-speaking citizens in our country are growing up in a language environment and have been studying in school for almost 10 years, with their oral and written communication in Uzbek significantly below the required level, necessitate identifying and addressing shortcomings in the teaching of the state language in our republic, updating second language teaching methods, and introducing intensive modern methods into the educational process. A study of the situation revealed the following problems related to the teaching and practice of the state language in our republic.

Motivational problems. It should be noted that a significant portion of citizens living in our country receive their education in schools and Russian language groups where instruction is conducted in other languages. Effective organization of Uzbek language instruction in these schools and groups is a matter of national importance. However, today:

despite the fact that foreign language instruction for children from an early age has been introduced, classes in the state language of our republic are not organized in Russian language groups;

the Uzbek language is taught in schools with foreign language instruction, rather than starting in the first grade, like other subjects (e.g., foreign languages).

the fact that the highest qualification level for teaching Uzbek in the continuous education system is level B2, which, as a result, does not allow for achieving levels C1 and C2 of state language education in the republic, has necessitated reforming the methodology of state language education and developing a national curriculum for teaching Uzbek in schools and groups with foreign language instruction.

Today, this is also required by the fundamental reforms being carried out in the education sector in our republic and the changes taking place based on Decree No. 5850 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically enhance the prestige and status of the Uzbek language as the state language."

The content issues. Despite significant efforts to create integrated programs and modernize textbooks on educational content in the Uzbek language in the general secondary

education system by grade: primary (grades 2–4), general secondary (grades 5–9), and high school (grades 10–11), the following serious shortcomings exist in the gradual continuation of this educational content in the vocational and higher education systems and in ensuring continuity between educational levels:

- in schools with instruction in other languages, the simultaneous teaching of the Uzbek and English Latin alphabets and spelling rules in the 2nd grade leads to incomplete mastery of standard skills by students. As a result, students confuse spelling rules, which leads to a sharp decline in writing literacy and a failure to master calligraphy skills.

- the combined teaching of Uzbek as the official language by students from Russian, Tajik, and related languages, whose proficiency in Uzbek varies, in the same group creates a number of difficulties in conveying content and assimilating material;

- the fact that Uzbek language textbooks are written with the same content for students from different language families creates difficulties for both teachers and students in the educational process.

Methodological problems. These problems include:

- The extremely small size and format of Uzbek language textbooks for grades 5–9 and the lack of accompanying teaching aids;

- Uzbek language teachers are not provided with methodological and educational literature, nor with additional didactic materials;

- The widespread introduction of new, effective methods, advanced pedagogical, and modern information technologies in Uzbek language education is not being implemented at the required level;

- Electronic textbooks, multimedia tools, and audio text collections have not been created;

- projects to create educational films and their targeted use in the educational process are not being implemented;

- a lack of scientific and methodological research into improving Uzbek language teaching methods, developing intensive teaching methods, modernizing textbooks, enhancing inactive Uzbek vocabulary at educational stages, and training personnel in professional and industry communication.

The staffing issues. The potential of teaching staff for Uzbek language teaching also does not meet the required level: while seven-language instruction is envisaged in the republic's general education schools, the closure of departments training teachers to teach Uzbek in schools where Russian and other fraternal languages are taught has led to teachers of other languages working in these same schools who have completed short-term professional development courses in these schools, leading to a decline in the quality of education.

In continuing education systems, Uzbek language instruction is often provided by teachers without specialized training. In-service training programs focus more on general pedagogical topics. Continuing education programs do not address strengthening teachers' theoretical and methodological knowledge in their specialty, and practical classes on teaching methods are not organized. In particular, the training of scientifically qualified personnel in Uzbek language teaching methods for foreign language groups is inadequately addressed.

CURRENT ISSUES IN IMPROVING LANGUAGE EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

The fact that our native language, as the state language of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is becoming the primary socio-economic and official language of communication in our country is

one of the great blessings of independence. Serious attention is being paid to citizens' literacy in the state language, particularly to the ability of representatives of other nationalities living in our republic to communicate freely in Uzbek, both orally and in writing. Today, interest in a rejuvenating Uzbekistan, its rich history and cultural heritage, and the unique spiritual values of the Uzbek people has led to the Uzbek language being studied at approximately sixty universities in countries such as the United States, Great Britain, Germany, France, Sweden, the Russian Federation, Ukraine, China, Japan, the Republic of Korea, India, Turkey, and Azerbaijan. Hundreds of Uzbek-language schools operate in neighboring countries such as Tajikistan, Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, and Kyrgyzstan. The number of foreign scholars and researchers conducting research in the Uzbek language and literature is increasing every year, contributing to the growing international prestige of the Uzbek language.

Based on the targets outlined in the State Program for the Development of the State Language for 2020–2030, the development of state language education in the continuous education system will be implemented in the following priority areas:

- creating broad opportunities and favorable conditions for the study of the Uzbek language by representatives of all nationalities and ethnic groups living in our country, as well as our compatriots living abroad, and foreigners wishing to learn the Uzbek language;

- developing the linguistic integrity inherent in our ancestors and the development of speech in preschool children, as well as creating special programs and teaching aids for kindergarten and preschool children to develop basic language learning skills from an early age, and ensuring that children of different nationalities living in our country begin to master the vocabulary of the state language from this stage and continue this learning continuously throughout their school education;

- ensuring the continuity of state language education between the systems of pre-school, general secondary and vocational, higher education by organizing training from the 1st grade in schools with foreign language instruction;

- improving the requirements of state standards for the state language of education, namely, establishing requirements for level A1 for pre-school and preparatory school institutions, for the content of education and qualification indicators of level A2 for primary education; establishing requirements for level B1 for grades 5-9, for level B2 for senior grades 10-11 and for level B1 for secondary specialized education; establishing standards for level C1 for higher education, level C2 for the philological direction of higher education and the level of advanced training, and also developing qualification requirements for graduates for each level of education;

- Ensure effective Uzbek language instruction, generate demand for its study, implement a certification system similar to that used for foreign languages in the Uzbek language, clearly define the legal status of certificates issued for each DTS level, and establish that 11th-grade, AL, and KHK graduates will be eligible to enter higher education institutions only if they meet the requirements of DTS level B2. Higher education graduates will be hired for professional positions in accordance with levels C1 and C2. This will also create a demand among all our citizens for an in-depth study of the state language of our republic;

- Considering that teaching methods for languages as native and as foreign or second languages vary worldwide, conduct specialized teacher training in the retraining and advanced training system on the theoretical and methodological aspects of teaching Uzbek to groups with other languages.

CONCEPTUAL PRINCIPLES FOR ENSURING CONTINUITY AND SUSTAINABILITY IN TEACHING THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

This Concept for Improving the Teaching of Uzbek as the State Language in Our Republic envisages the introduction of scientifically based new conceptual principles for teaching Uzbek at all levels of education in our republic and the development of the following competencies and practical language skills in students through ensuring continuity and academic succession:

- Improving state educational standards and qualification requirements for graduates at each level of education in accordance with advanced international practices in teaching the Uzbek language in the current linguistic environment;

- Teaching Uzbek words and pronunciation of Uzbek speech sounds in preschool and preparatory Russian groups from an early age using the "Zullisonayn" method; developing listening skills, understanding, and pronunciation of letters individually and in words in preschool and preparatory Russian groups using visual aids;

- Begin teaching the Uzbek language in elementary grades, starting in the first grade. Introduce students to the speech sounds of the Uzbek alphabet separately and in cursive in the first semester. Beginning in the second semester, develop reading and writing skills by teaching them to write letters in accordance with the requirements of Khusnikhat (the rules of the khusnikhat).

- Develop a methodology for expanding Uzbek vocabulary through game-based learning, poems, songs, riddles, and fairy tales, based on the physiological age characteristics of preschoolers and primary school students.

- In grades 1-4, expand students' vocabulary and develop practical listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills by teaching them to compose short texts from words, phrases, and short, simple, monosyllabic sentences.

- In grades 5-9, systematically expand students' vocabulary by activating inactive words presented in speech topics and systematically teach the grammatical foundations of composing texts with phrases, sentences, and sentences based on orthoepic and spelling rules, as well as develop students' practical language and speech competencies by expanding their literary reading;

- In grades 10-11, teach the grammatical foundations of expressing thoughts in simple and complex sentences, and develop skills in the integrated use of speech actions—listening, speaking, reading, and writing—based on literary reading materials;

- At the secondary vocational education stage, develop students' skills in the practical application of acquired knowledge in their chosen professional specialty and mastered Uzbek language terminology, and develop skills in composing coherent texts on professional and business topics and writing in the state language;

- at the stage of higher education, developing students' skills in writing in a scientific style in the Uzbek language, freely working with intra-industry documents, participating in meetings and conferences held in the specialty, with their own reports;

- develop literary reading material from simple to complex and integrate words and their grammatical forms into speech, presenting them in accordance with speech and grammar topics; develop students' vocabulary based on the norms of the literary language;

- expand students' horizons using literary reading material; teach them to think independently, make independent decisions in problematic situations, think creatively, and feel and appreciate national spiritual values;

- strengthen interdisciplinary connections based on the speech skills developed in students during their Uzbek language education, that is, develop competencies in the free application of

knowledge acquired in various disciplines, and at higher levels of education – knowledge in their specialization, in dialogic, monologue, and polylogue speech.

CONCLUSION

It has been shown through analysis that implementation of this promising concept for teaching Uzbek to speakers of other languages will enable the creation of a systematic program for in-depth study of the Uzbek language, ensuring continuity and consistency in Uzbek language instruction across educational levels, where the first level at each educational level will serve as the foundation for the next, and one level will seamlessly continue with the next. Also:

- creation of a new generation of teaching and methodological materials for teaching the Uzbek language across educational levels (textbook, notebook, teacher's manual, multimedia supplement to textbooks, etc.); development of a series of manuals "Uzbek Language," "My Book is My Sun," and "My Word is My Pearl" based on the "First Step" program, aimed at preparing young children for school education in preschool educational institutions and preparatory groups;

- Modernization of Uzbek language textbooks and teaching aids, creation of multimedia resources and educational films that ensure the integration of specialized subjects and the Uzbek language in vocational and higher education;

- Updating teaching aids to organize Uzbek language lessons in an engaging and meaningful format, ensuring their effectiveness, enriching the content of textbooks and teaching aids, in particular, the creation of children's poems, stories, and songs aimed at teaching the pronunciation of Uzbek speech sounds and new words for preschools and elementary grades, which are considered the foundation of education;

- Establishing cooperation with the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan and composers, commissioning children's poets and writers, composers, and young artists to write children's poems, stories, and create short songs for educational purposes, as well as paying serious attention to building a reserve of teaching aids for the Uzbek language by announcing special competitions;

- The development of teaching aids aimed at specialized teacher training in the retraining and advanced training system in the theoretical and methodological aspects of teaching Uzbek to foreign-language groups will contribute to the creation of broad opportunities and favorable conditions for representatives of different nationalities living in our republic to gain a solid mastery of the state language and further enhance the prestige of the Uzbek language.

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